

Assessment of Out-Of-Service Teachers ... (Tanimu & Rabi, 2023) DOI:

Assessment of Out-Of-Service Teachers in Teaching and Learning of Mathematics at Primary School Level in Lere Educational Zone, Kaduna State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study aims at investigation of the Assessment of out-of-service teachers in teaching and learning of Mathematics at Primary School level in Lere Educational Zone, Kaduna State, Nigeria. A descriptive survey research design was used for the study and a self-developed questionnaire named Upper Primary School Teacher Questionnaire (UPSTQ) with nineteen (19) items were used for data collection with 0.65 reliability index. The instruments were validated by three experts whose rank are senior lectures and above, two from Department of Science Education, Ahmadu Bello University Zaria and one from Department of Mathematics, Federal College of Education Zaria. Three (3) objectives, three (3) research questions and three (3) null hypotheses, respectively were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance to guide the conduct of the study. The Population of the study consists of all upper basic primary school teachers in Lere Educational Zone during the 2021/2022 academic session. A sample size of 37 Upper basic primary school teachers were used for the study. Data collected were analyzed using frequency count and simple percentages. It was discovered that, there was no significant area(s) in the primary school Mathematics curriculum where the teachers find it difficult to teach or require further training before they can adequately teach the topics. Based on the findings, it was recommended that regular workshops and seminar should be organized either by ministry of education or relevant governmental and non-governmental organizations to address identified difficult areas where the teachers felt incompetent to teach.

Keyword: Mathematics, Teaching and learning, Teachers

Introduction

The foundation of any planned program mostly determines its quality, effectiveness and the extent to which its objectives can be realized. The ability to analyze, synthesize and comprehend a given concept lies on the mastery of its foundation. Education is systematically organized and subjects are generally intersected, concepts or topics are specially linked from simple to complex as pre-requisite. In primary schools, the subjects are served as the base or foundation to which further studies may be place on and a preparation for life challenges. Odili (2006), defined Mathematics as the science of quantity and space, "it is a systematized, organized and exact branch of science". It is a creation of human mind, concerned primarily with ideas, processes and reasoning. Ashraft and Kirk (2010), indicated that mathematics is the language of science and foundation of rational development and productivity. Akine (2017) remarked that as long as mathematics are in the classroom and isolated from acquiring mathematics experiences, they are more likely to need some updating. Harmit (2017) defined mathematical updating as the mathematical knowledge and skills needed by mathematics teachers to provide their students with up-to-date preparation for the current technology of the world of work. Mathematics teachers need periodic in-service training to update their competence in their areas of specialization. It seems most teachers at primary schools denied these opportunities of re-training. Some of the objectives of primary school education as stipulated in National Policy on Education (FRN, 2013) include;

1. Inculcation of permanent literacy and numeracy,
2. Laying a foundation for national development,
3. Giving the child opportunities for developing manipulative and scientific skills

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At all levels of education, the primary school is still the first level of educational ladder (Okeke, 2016). He further maintained that; primary school is a preparatory ground where the background knowledge is rooted and built up for other academic endeavor. Specifically, the objectives of primary school mathematics curriculum include;

1. Developing positive attitudes of the pupils toward mathematics and appreciation of both the practical and aesthetic aspects,
2. To develop problem solving abilities and a facility for application of mathematics to everyday life,
3. To enable the child to use mathematical language effectively and accurately,
4. To enable the child, acquire an understanding of mathematical concepts and process to his/her appropriate level of development and ability,
5. To enable the child to acquire the proficiency in fundamental mathematics skills and in recalling basic number acts.

This indicates that; there is need to lay a sound foundation of mathematics knowledge at primary school so as to ensure the realization of its objectives. The primary school level is often considered to be the most important years of child school career (Lawrence, 2015). Teachers are the curriculum implementers; therefore, every teacher should act as architect, composer, movies director, stock broker, ship captain, and prospector (Aminu et al, 2016). This will put the pupils at ease, develop in them positive attitude towards the learning of mathematics and thus, increase their performance.

Despite the vital roles played by mathematics in scientific and technological development of the nation, its teaching and learning are faced with some problems that make most students to perform poorly in the subject. According to Onifade (2016), academic performance is an important aspect of learning but retaining what is learnt seems to be more important. This might have resulted from weak and erroneous foundation they receive at early stage as a result of difficulties faced by the teachers who are not scientifically based or are not specialized in mathematics in some selected upper basic primary school classes, which made them to teach the topics poorly, wrongly, partially, or even skip or ignore some of the topics. Akinsolu (2010), observed that teachers are vital pre-requisites for students' attainment of educational goals and objectives. Similarly, Ashimole (2011), emphasized that teaching and learning depends largely on teacher, and that it is on teachers' number, quality and devotion that rest the effectiveness of all educational arrangements, development and growth. The teacher is ultimately responsible for translating educational policies and principles into actions based on practice during interaction with the pupils. This is because no education can go beyond the quality of its teacher. This observation becomes a challenge and this is why the current effort is being embarked upon to verify the claim. Therefore, the need to investigate on Assessment of out-of-service teachers in teaching and learning of Mathematics at Primary School level in Lere Educational Zone, Kaduna State, Nigeria cannot be over emphasized.

Objectives of the Study

The purpose of this study was to investigate on the 'Assessment of out-of-service teachers in teaching and learning of Mathematics at Primary School level in Lere Educational Zone, Kaduna State, Nigeria'. The study aimed to determine the effectiveness of teaching mathematics subject at upper primary schools by out-of-service teachers, where one teacher has to teach all the subjects offered by the pupils irrespective of his/her area of specialization.

Specifically, the study aimed to;

1. Find out if there exist challenges encountered by the out-of-service teachers teaching mathematics at upper basic primary schools in Lere educational zone.
2. Find out difficult topics encountered by out-of-service mathematics teachers at upper basic primary school level in Lere educational zone.
3. Assess relationship between out-of-service teachers and pupils' performance in mathematics at primary school level in Lere educational zone

Research Questions

The following research questions were asked to guide the conduct of the study;

1. what are the challenges encountered by the out-of-service teachers in teaching of mathematics at upper primary school level in Lere educational zone?
2. What are the difficult topics encountered by the out-of-service mathematics teachers at upper basic primary school in Lere educational zone?
3. What is the relationship between out-of-service teachers and pupils' performance in mathematics at primary school level in Lere educational zone?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study;

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1. There are no significant challenges encountered by out-of-service teachers in teaching mathematics at upper basic primary school level in Lere educational zone.
2. There is no significant difficult topics encountered by out-of-service mathematics teachers at upper basic primary school level in Lere educational zone
3. There is no significant relationship between out-of-service teachers and pupils' performance in mathematics at primary school level in Lere educational zone.

Methodology

The research design used for this study was a descriptive survey. Data were collected from the selected sample of the study. The Population of the study consists of all upper basic primary school teachers in Lere Educational Zone during the 2021/2022 academic session. A sample size of 37 Upper basic primary school teachers were used for the study. Data collected were analyzed using frequency count and simple percentages. It was discovered that, there was no significant area(s) in the primary school Mathematics curriculum where the teachers find it difficult to teach to teach or require further training before they can adequately teach the topics. A questionnaire named; Upper Primary School Teachers Questionnaire (UPSTQ) with nineteen (19) items was used for data collection. The instrument was validated by three experts whose rank are senior lecturers and above, two from Department of Science Education, Ahmadu Bello University Zaria and one from Department of Mathematics, Federal College of Education Zaria. Their corrections were noted and incorporated. The reliability of the instruments was tested using test re-test reliability test and was found to be 0.65 which implies that the instrument is reliable. The administration and collection of the questionnaire were done by the researcher with the help of the heads of the schools. Questionnaires were distributed and collected latter through the head teachers of the schools. Forty-eight (48) questionnaires were distributed while only thirty-seven (37) were returned. These questionnaires were sorted based on identical opinions of the respondents for easy tabulation. For analyzing hypotheses, the row data collected through the method of research instrument were processed and prepared for presentation as tabulated evidences. The technique used in constructing these tables include; frequency and percentage calculations. Thus, all the conclusions about the findings of this study were made on the bases of percentage of the responses recorded. The tables were prepared to serve as the main frame-work around which the analyses, conclusions and recommendations were made.

Result

Research Question 1:

What are the challenges encountered by the out-of-service teachers in teaching of mathematics at upper primary school level in Lere educational zone?

Table 1: Frequency and percentage of teachers having problems in teaching some selected topics at upper primary school.

S/N	TOPIC	NUMBER OF TEACHERS	PERCENTAGE (%)
1.	Probability	1	03.0
2.	Geometry	2	05.4
3.	Angles	2	05.4
4.	Weight	1	03.0
5.	Measurement	2	05.4
6.	Division	5	14.0
7.	Word Problem	6	16.2
8.	Numbers base	1	03.0
9.	Ratio	4	11.0
10.	Proportion	1	03.0
11.	Expansion	1	03.0
12.	Roman numerals	1	03.0
13.	L.C.M. (Least Common Multiples)	1	03.0
14.	Counting in millions	1	03.0
15.	Percentage	4	11.0
16.	Algebra	1	03.0
17.	Indices	2	05.4
18.	Quantitative reasoning	4	11.0

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19.	Order of operation	2	02.7
20.	Capacity	4	11.0
21.	Fraction	2	05.4
22.	Factorization	1	03.0
23.	Construction	1	03.0
24.	Shapes	2	05.4
25.	Plain Figures	2	05.4
26.	Scale drawing	1	03.0
27.	Data collection and Presentation	2	05.4
28.	Measure of central tendency	1	03.0
29.	Binary numbers	3	08.1
30.	Volume	1	03.0
31.	Height	1	03.0
32.	Money	2	05.4
33.	Decimal	2	05.4

The result from table 1 reveals that; teachers rate themselves having no problem to teach more than 90% of the upper primary school curriculum content since none of the topics indicates 50% of the teachers having problem to teach.

Research question 2

What are the difficult topics encountered by the out-of-service mathematics teachers at upper basic primary school in Lere educational zone?

Table 2: Frequency and percentage of Teachers having difficulty in teaching some selected topics at upper primary school

S/N	TOPIC	NUMBER OF TEACHERS	PERCENTAGE (%)
1.	Probability	1	03.0
2.	Geometry	2	05.4
3.	Angles	2	05.4
4.	Weight	1	03.0
5.	Measurement	2	05.4
6.	Division	5	14.0
7.	Word Problem	6	16.2
8.	Numbers base	1	03.0
9.	Ratio	4	10.8
10.	Proportion	1	03.0
11.	Expansion	1	03.0
12.	Roman numerals	1	03.0
13.	L.C.M. (Least Common Multiples)	1	03.0
14.	Counting in millions	1	03.0
15.	Percentage	4	10.8
16.	Algebra	1	03.0
17.	Indices	2	05.4
18.	Quantitative reasoning	4	11.0
19.	Order of operation	2	02.7
20.	Capacity	4	11.0
21.	Fraction	2	05.4
22.	Factorization	1	03.0
23.	Construction	1	03.0
24.	Shapes	2	05.4
25.	Plain Figures	2	05.4
26.	Scale drawing	1	03.0
27.	Data collection and Presentation	2	05.4

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28.	Measure of central tendency	1	03.0
29.	Binary numbers	3	08.1
30.	Volume	1	03.0
31.	Height	1	03.0
32.	Money	2	05.4
33.	Decimal	2	05.4

The result from table 2 reveals the percentage of the teachers having difficulty in teaching some selected topics in the upper primary school mathematics curriculum. However, the items listed were those items which the teacher said they are having problem to teach thus, they need further training before they can competently teach the topics. Those who require this training were mainly those teachers who find themselves to teach the subject of mathematics and do not specialize in mathematics.

Research question 3

What is the relationship between out-of-service teachers and pupils' performance in mathematics at primary school level in Lere educational zone?

Table 3: Frequency and percentage of teachers supporting and not supporting teacher far class

S/N	Names of Schools	Teachers' Frequency	Supporting	Percentage (%) of Supporting	Not supporting	Percentage (%) of not Supporting
1.	L.G.E.A. Pri. Sch. Rahama	3	3	100	0	0
2.	L.G.E.A. Pri. Sch. Saminaka B.	3	3	100	0	0
3.	L.G.E.A. Pri. Sch. U/mele	1	1	100	0	0
4.	U.B.E. Pri. Sch. Kafannuwa	1	1	100	0	0
5.	U.B.E. Pri. Sch. T/wada	3	1	33.3	2	66.7
6.	U.B.E. Pri. Sch. Nasarawa	2	2	100	0	0
7.	U.B.E. Pri. Sch. Badarawa	2	2	100	0	0
8.	L.G.E.A. Pri. Sch. U/Jumare	2	2	100	0	0
9.	L.G.E.A. Pri. Sch. Abadawa I	2	2	100	0	0
10.	U.B.E. Pri. Sch. Abadawa II	2	2	100	0	0
11.	U.B.E. Pri. Sch. Domawa	1	1	100	0	0
12.	U.B.E. Pri. Sch. Lagga	1	1	100	0	0
13.	U.B.E. Pri. Sch. Kwaftara	1	1	100	0	0
14.	U.B.E. Pri. Sch. Sabon-birni I	2	2	100	0	0
15.	Central Primary School U/Bawa	3	3	100	0	0
16.	U.B.E. Pri. Sch. Nasarawan- jaja	1	1	100	0	0

Table 3 reveals that about 93.3% (28 out of 30) of the teachers support the policy of every teacher should teach his/her area of specialization. One of their reasons among others was that; pupils will have an effective teaching ones the teacher is competent in his subject matter. This indicates that only 6.3 % (2 out of 30) of the teachers support the policy of teacher per class. Their reason among others was that; the teacher will have enough time to access his/her students without any interruption by other teachers. The researcher remarks here that; it is possible for a teacher to be competent on a particular subject matter and not on others, no matter how intelligent the teacher is. Therefore, the researcher is in line with those teachers who support the policy of every teacher should teach his/her area of specialization.

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Discussion of Findings

The findings reveal the topics where the teachers are having problem to teach as shown in Table 1. These topics were similar to those topics where the teachers rate themselves as the areas, they are having difficulty to teach as shown in and Table 2. Thus, the teachers require further training before they can teach these topics competently. Although the teachers listed about thirty-three topics out of the upper primary school mathematics curriculum as those topics, they are having difficulty to teach, the majority of the teachers support the policy of every teacher should teach his/her area of specialization. Attached to this, many teachers are just being involve in to teaching mathematics so they have little or no background experience. This is a clear manifestation of the poor pre-service training they had. Thus, the problem faced by the teachers ranges from poor teaching of most of the topics, act of skipping some topic/selecting the simple arithmetic such as Addition, Subtraction, Division and Multiplication in the upper primary school mathematics curriculum. In fact, through discussion with teacher by the researcher, some of the teachers identify only Addition and Subtraction as topics they can manage to teach. This appears to be a great problem to the performance of the pupils since the background of the subject will not be there.

Conclusions

Based on the findings from this study, the researcher concluded that the ability of the teachers has been discovered to be very okay since majority of the teachers perceive themselves very competent to teach at least more than 50% of the upper primary school curriculum content.

Finally, it is concluded that, poor performance among primary school pupils may not be as a result of difficult topics faced by the teachers in Lere educational zone, Kaduna State, Nigeria. Thus, poor performance may be as a result of out-of-service teachers since about 93% of the teachers support the policy of every teacher should teach based on his/her area of specialization.

Recommendations

Based on the findings from this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Regular workshops and seminar should be organized either by ministry of education or relevant governmental and non-governmental organizations to address identified difficult areas where the teachers felt incompetent to teach.
2. Re-fresher training should be organized by the state ministry of education on regular bases as the content of mathematics is dynamic in order to improve the level of effectiveness of the achievement of the stated objectives of the content.
3. Specialist in mathematics education should be employed as a matter of urgent need by the Kaduna State government so as to carter for the need of the Pupils in order to improve their performance in mathematics and to reduce level of complications faced by the teacher.

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